

MOF-Derived Nanoceria/Graphitic Carbon Nitride as an Efficient Electrochemical Modifier for Guanine Sensor with Diffusional Response

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Abstract. This work presents a novel approach for the electrochemical detection of guanine (GU) using a MOF-derived nanomaterial. CeBTC MOF-derived CeO₂ nanoparticles, prepared by calcination and mixed with graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) were structurally and electrochemically characterized and further applied in sensing of GU. XRPD, FTIR, SEM, and XPS measurements were used to study the composition, structure, and morphology of the nanoceria/g-C₃N₄ electrode modifier. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements and cyclic voltammetric studies indicated an improved electrocatalytic output of nanoceria/g-C₃N₄ modified carbon paste electrode (MOFdCeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE). The optimal content of electrode modifier in CPE, experimental conditions, and analytical technique parameters were established to achieve sensitive quantification of GU. Kinetic parameters of the electrochemical reaction of GU were determined and a diffusional response at an electrochemical sensor was achieved. The linear working range of the developed square-wave voltammetric method (SWV) in Britton Robinson buffer solution pH 3.0 at MOFdCeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE was recorded from 0.5 μM to 100 μM of GU, with a detection limit of 0.12 μM. The proposed guanine sensor showed good storage stability, repeatability, and selectivity, and its real sample applicability was successfully tested by quantification of guanine in spiked urine samples, with excellent accuracy and precision.

Keywords: CeBTC, nanoceria, carbon paste electrode, guanine determination, diffusional response

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), the orderly structure of metal nodes in organic linkers, have drawn scientific attention due to their superior material properties. Based on high chemical stability, relatively large specific surface areas, high porosity, and tunable structure, MOFs and MOF-derived materials are found their possible applications in catalysis, batteries, conversion, separation, and gas sensors [1,2]. Functional nanostructures can be easily and successfully prepared by thermolysis of MOFs. Besides conventional methods for synthesizing of metal-oxide nanoparticles [3], they could also be obtained from MOFs. These frameworks represent flexible templates that, through a controlled thermal decomposition process, can produce oxide nanoparticles with even the dispersion of metals on its network. In recent times, various metal oxides like NiO, CeO₂, CuO, Fe₂O₃, Co₃O₄, PdCoO_x and others have been obtained in this way and electrochemically applied as energy storage devices [4,5], for catalysis

[6,7] and degradation [8], for determining total antioxidant capacity [9] and employed as sensors [10,11].

Guanine, a derivative of purine, is one of the main nucleotide bases found in DNA and RNA. Detecting guanine using electrochemical sensors has gained significant attention due to its role in biological processes [12,13] and as an indicator of oxidative DNA damage [14]. Although GU was electrochemically determined by different methods and modified electrodes [15–26] it is still a challenge to determine low concentrations of this compound, usually present in small amounts in biological complex matrices [27]. Fouling of the electrode surface is another problematic issue, and it is connected with absorption of guanine oxidation products on it. This leads to the decrease in sensitivity and reproducibility of guanine determination over time, affecting the stability and efficiency of the sensor itself [15]. Electrochemical determination of nanomolar concentrations of guanine was achieved on molecularly imprinted polymer-based electrochemical sensor [16], while recently reported highly sensitive determination of purine bases on ZIF-8-derived hollow N-doped carbon dodecahedron and AuNPs [17] which draw attention on the possibility of successful application of MOF derived nanostructures in composite materials for efficient determining of guanine.

Based on the exceptional catalytic properties of nanoceria (CeO_2 NPs), originating from its potential of reversible switching valence $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ [28] we assumed the possibility that MOF derived CeO_2 nanostructures could enhance guanine oxidation signals. CeMOFs can be synthesized with different organic linkers [29], and H_3BTC (benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid) based CeMOF (CeBTC) is the most used as a precursor for obtaining nanoceria for catalytic purposes [30].

We have previously studied a combination of metal or metal oxide nanoparticles with carbonaceous materials. They have shown excellent catalytic performance and have been successfully incorporated into electrochemical sensors for the detection of biocompounds [31–34]. Still, in this work, we explored a new approach to develop a nanocomposite modifier by utilizing metal-oxide nanoparticles prepared by thermolysis of the metal-organic framework. We synthesized CeBTC in an aqueous solution at low temperature. Further, we used it as a dispersion precursor for forming porous CeO_2 NPs with uniformly encapsulated cerium ions, controlling the agglomeration. Thermal decomposition was achieved by simple calcination of CeBTC at $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air, and obtained cerium(IV) oxide particle size was at the nano level and the average crystallite size was about 7 nm. To enhance electrical conductivity and performance, MOF-derived CeO_2 NPs were combined with a two-dimensional graphitic carbon nitride network (g- C_3N_4) to create a highly conductive and efficient modifier for carbon

paste electrodes. The kinetic parameters of the electrode process were determined and, a stable diffusion-controlled response was achieved. The developed electrochemical sensor was successfully applied to the quantitative analysis of guanine in spiked human urine samples, demonstrating its reliability and practical utility.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Chemicals

Cerium(III)-chloride heptahydrate and benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid (BTC), used as a linker for the synthesis of CeBTC, were acquired from Alfa Aesar (USA). Urea, guanine hydrochloride, paraffin oil, and glassy carbon powder (for preparing CPE) were all products of Sigma Aldrich company (USA). All other chemicals used for preparing of the electrolyte (Britton-Robinson buffer), electrochemical characterization, preparing samples, and in selectivity study were reagent grade. Ultrapure water was produced from the Millipore Milli Q system.

2.2 Preparation of CeBTC, g-C₃N₄ and MOF derived nanoceria

CeBTC metal-organic framework was synthesized by a slightly modified previously used procedure [35]. The first solution was obtained by mixing 0.25 mmol of CeCl₃·7H₂O with ultrapure water to obtain a 50 mL solution. In the second solution, 0.25 mmol of benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid was dissolved in 50 mL of ethanol/water solution (*v/v* = 1:1) under vigorous stirring at room temperature. These two solutions were mixed under a continuous stirring for 1.5 h. A white precipitate of CeBTC was collected by centrifugation, washed several times with ethanol/water (*v/v*, 1:1), and then dried at 60 °C. CeO₂ NPs were derived by calcination of as-prepared CeBTC at a temperature of 450 °C at 10 °C/min and held at the final temperature for 3 h. After that, the products were cooled down to room temperature naturally.

Graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) was synthesized through a simple calcination approach placing 5 g of urea in a ceramic crucible with a cover under ambient pressure in air. Then, the closed crucible was heated in a muffle furnace at 550 °C at a 3 °C/min ramp rate for 3 h. The resulting yellow-colored g-C₃N₄ powder was ground with agate mortar and stored for further electrode modifier preparation.

2.3 Methods and Instrumentation

The crystal structures of the synthesized MOF and its corresponding oxide were determined through X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) analysis. Dried powder samples were examined

using a Smart Lab[®] high-resolution diffractometer (Rigaku, Japan) provided with a CuK α source of radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) working at 40 kV and 30 mA. Diffraction patterns were measured within the 2θ range of 5-70 $^\circ$.

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was used to examine the surface chemistry of the prepared MOF and MOF-derived nanoparticles within the mid-infrared region (4000-400 cm^{-1}). A Nicolet iS50 FT-IR spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) with a Smart iTR ATR accessory was employed for the analysis. Powdered samples were pressed on a diamond crystal plate using a pivot press to ensure the optimum exposure to the infrared beam. Background spectra collected from a clean diamond crystal were subtracted using OMNIC[™] Spectra Software.

The morphology of Ce-MOF and MOF/CeO₂/g-C₃N₄ samples was observed by FE-SEM using a MIRA 3 XMU instrument (TESCAN, Brno, Czech Republic), operated at 20 keV, after deposition of a tin gold layer in sputter coater Polaron SC502 (Fisons Instruments, UK).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed using an ESCALAB MkII electron spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) with a base pressure of 5×10^{-10} mbar in the analysis chamber. A non-monochromated AlK α X-ray source (1486.6 eV) was used with a pass energy of 20 eV to record high-resolution spectra. A pass energy of 20 eV was used for the hemispherical analyzer. The instrumental resolution, measured as the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Ag3d_{5/2} photoelectron peak, was approximately 1 eV. The data was analyzed using Casa XPS software (Casa Software Ltd). The measured spectra were processed to remove X-ray satellites and Shirley-type background. [36]. Peak positions and areas were determined by fitting symmetrical Gaussian-Lorentzian curves. The relative concentrations of the different chemical species were calculated by normalizing the peak areas to their corresponding photoionization cross-sections, as determined by Scofield [37].

Autolab 302 N potentiostat/galvanostat and software NOVA 2.0.2 were used for electrochemical measurements. Cyclic voltammetric (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were done in the presence of a redox test solution of 5 mM K₃[Fe(CN)]₆/K₄[Fe(CN)]₆ (1:1) mixture dissolved in 0.1 M KCl. The electrochemical working cell with a three-electrode system was used for experiments. An Ag/AgCl (saturated KCl) was the reference electrode, a Pt-wire was used as a counter electrode and a modified carbon paste electrode was employed as a working electrode. For EIS measurements the frequency was changed from $1 \cdot 10^5$ Hz to $1 \cdot 10^2$ Hz with a signal amplitude of 5 mV at the potential of 0.05 V. The optimal SWV parameters were found by varying pulse amplitude from 10 to 90 mV, frequency from 10 to 90 Hz, and potential step from 2 to 10 mV/s.

2.4 Fabrication of MOF_dCeO₂/g-C₃N₄ modified CPE

A binary composite electrode modifier was prepared by mixing MOF-derived nanoceria and graphitic carbon nitride in a ratio of 3:1 in dimethyl formamide, stirred in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min, and allowed to dry at 40 °C. The powder was collected and used as an electrode modifier, which was used as an electrochemical platform in this research was produced by mixing paraffin oil and glassy carbon powder in a mortar, in a ratio of 1:4. Three modified electrodes were prepared using 5%, 10%, and 15% of the modifier relative to the amount of carbon powder. The MOF_dCeO₂-CPE and g-C₃N₄-CPE electrodes were prepared using the same procedure. After standing overnight a portion of the resulting paste was used to fill the carbon paste electrode holder, and the surface was polished using a PTFE plate or wet filter paper before every measurement. The carbon paste was modified by adding a certain percentage (m/m) of the synthesized modifier.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Material structure and morphology study

The crystal structures of the samples were determined by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns are shown in **Fig. 1a**. Diffraction patterns confirmed the formation of the desired metal-organic framework, Ce-MOF, based on cerium linked to BTC [35]. The thermally decomposed products were also characterized by XRPD. **Fig. 1a** shows the formation of pure cubic MOF-derived CeO₂ (indexed in Fm-3m, No. 225 crystal phase) with an average crystallite size of approximately 7 nm after the calcination of CeBTC [38]. The average crystallite size was estimated using the Scherrer equation: $B(2\theta) = K\lambda/L \cdot \cos\theta$, where $B(2\theta)$ is the peak width at a specific 2θ value, λ is the X-ray wavelength, L is the crystallite size. K is a constant typically assumed to be 1.0 for spherical particles. The Scherrer equation relates the peak broadening in an X-ray diffraction pattern to the crystallite size.

The ATR-FTIR spectra of CeBTC and MOF_dCeO₂ show peaks between 630 and 760 cm⁻¹, attributed to in-plane and out-of-plane bending vibrations of the aromatic ring (**Fig. 1b**). The band around 1110 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric C–O stretching vibrations of the carboxylate groups. Strong absorption bands at 1365, 1428, and 1608 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of carboxylate group vibrations in mesoporous CeBTC, consistent with the asymmetric, symmetric C=O stretching modes and C–O stretching mode associated with the binding of carboxylate (COOH) groups to Ce ions [39]. Most of these bands, along with the characteristic bands of the COO⁻ groups of BTC₃⁻, are observed in the FTIR spectrum. The

band around 486 cm^{-1} is attributed to the O–Ce–O stretching vibration. The vibrations at 3400 cm^{-1} were observed due to the adsorbed water on the surface.

Figure 1. a) XRPD diffraction patterns of CeBTC (*below*) and MOF-derived cerium oxide after the calcination (*above*) and b) ATR-FTIR spectra of CeBTC and MOFdCeO₂.

The morphology of Ce-MOF and MOFdCeO₂/g-C₃N₄ particles is shown in **Fig. 2**. Urchin-like agglomerates of a few microns in size, composed of rod-shaped particles, were dominant in both cases at 10,000x magnification (**Fig. 2a,d**). A certain amount of deagglomerated Ce-MOF particles is also visible at higher magnifications. Ce-MOF rod-shaped nanoparticles were observed at high magnification, confirming the nanostructure of the particles (**Fig. 2b, c**). In the case of composite MOFdCeO₂/g-C₃N₄ powder, two different levels of contrast related to two different morphologies were visible at 50,000x and 100,000x magnification. The first morphology is similar to that of Ce-MOF (**Fig. 2e**), while the second shows a porous graphitic carbon nitride structure with incorporated deagglomerated nanoparticles of CeO₂ (**Fig. 2f**).

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of: a,b,c) Ce-MOF; d,e,f) MOF/CeO₂/g-C₃N₄ powders.

The oxidation states and surface atomic concentrations of the elements present on the surface of the CeO₂ nanoparticle sample were investigated using Electron Spectroscopy for Chemical Analysis, commonly known as X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). The survey spectra of the light-yellow CeO₂ powder sample, measured using AlK α (blue line) and MgK α (red line) radiation, are presented in **Fig. 3a**. The XPS data reveal core-level peaks corresponding to cerium (Ce 3d) and oxygen (O 1s), which constitute the nanoparticles. Additionally, trace amounts of chlorine (Cl 2p core-level) and carbon (C 1s core-level) from the preparation process are also detected. Further insights can be obtained from the high-resolution XP spectra shown in **Fig. 3b, c**.

Figure 3. a) XP survey spectra of CeO₂ powder nanoparticles sample. The blue curve was recorded with AlK α irradiation, while the red curve was recorded with MgK α irradiation. High-resolution XP curve-fitted spectra of CeO₂ nanoparticles: (b) Ce 3d core-level; (c) O 1s core-level.

The Ce 3d core-level region is depicted in **Fig. 3b**. The curve's line shape corresponds to the 3d_{5/2} peak with a binding energy of 882.5 eV, accompanied by the 3d_{3/2} peak at 898.3 eV, and a satellite peak at a binding energy of 916.9 eV, characteristic for Ce⁴⁺ oxidation state. Consequently, we attribute the oxidation state of cerium predominantly to Ce⁴⁺, consistent with the findings of Maslakov et al. (2018) [40]. However, closer inspection reveals a slight deviation from the standard line shape associated with the Ce⁴⁺ oxidation state, suggesting that a portion of the cerium on the surface may exist in the reduced Ce³⁺ oxidation state. It is well known that X-ray irradiation can disrupt the bonds between cerium and oxygen, potentially leading to the formation of Ce³⁺. To mitigate this effect, we performed careful measurements, reducing the exposure time to less than 5 minutes to prevent X-ray-induced reduction while maintaining spectrum quality. By applying the curve-fitting procedure described by Matolín et al. [41], we estimated the ratio of Ce³⁺ to Ce⁴⁺ on the surface of the CeO₂ nanoparticles to be 0.15. The presence of Ce³⁺ can be attributed to dangling bonds on the nanoparticle surface. The high-resolution XP spectrum of the O 1s core-level is shown in **Fig. 3c**. Curve fitting reveals the components of the O 1s peak, with a peak at 529.4 eV corresponding to Ce-O bonds, as expected, and a peak at 531.0 eV indicating non-lattice oxygen and/or oxygen defects with low coordination. A minor concentration of oxygen bonded to organic species, originating from the nanoparticle preparation process, was also detected at 527.8 eV binding energy. Considering the surface atomic concentrations of total cerium and oxygen, excluding carbon and chlorine

contamination, we calculated a Ce/O ratio of 0.43 from the XPS data. This ratio is close to the theoretical value of 0.5 for CeO₂. The slight discrepancy between the experimental and theoretical ratios is primarily due to the presence of Ce³⁺ on the nanoparticle surface, with additional contributions from standard errors in the XPS experiment. The XPS data and analysis indicate that the CeO₂ nanoparticles possess a minor concentration of reduced Ce³⁺ ions on their surface.

3.2 Electrochemical characterization of electrode material

The combination of CeO₂ nanoparticles and graphite carbon nitride intrigued the researchers and this binary electrode material was investigated before [42,43]. Recently, polyaniline-supported g-C₃N₄/CeO₂ was employed as a chemosensor for selected heavy ions [44]. Pyrolysis decomposed Ce-MOF/g-C₃N₄ was used for sensing dopamine [10] while graphite carbon nitride was doped with MOF-derived CeO₂ to produce photocatalyst for H₂ production [45].

Contrary to the last-mentioned study, in this work, we use CeO₂/g-C₃N₄ composite material as electrode modifier and MOF-derived nanoceria nanoparticles were dominant in its composition. Our previous CV and EIS investigations in [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox system showed that the most conductive electrode modifier was obtained when nanoceria and g-C₃N₄ were mixed in 3:1, and that ratio was detained in further experiments.

Based on the results of CV and EIS measurements in [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} test solution, the electrochemical properties of electrode modifiers were explored and the optimal material and its composition were chosen. Comparing the influence of each of the modifiers, it can be concluded that the tested cerium dioxide significantly increases the intensity of the currents (20%) obtained for both oxidation and reduction processes about the unmodified electrode, confirming its excellent electrocatalytic capabilities. On the other hand, the graphite carbon nitride itself, due to its highly conductive nature, increases the electroactive surface area of the electrode, which results in a decrease in the difference in the potentials (ΔE) of the oxidation and reduction peaks, from $\Delta E_{\text{pristineCPE}} = 202$ mV to $\Delta E_{\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4} = 98$ mV. Finally, their synergetic effect is shown through an increase in current by about 60% and reduced peak-to-peak separation compared to the unmodified electrode, which shows that the composite has a significant improvement in electrocatalytic ability, which is reflected in a significant increase in diffusion, mass transfer, and charge transfer.

CV profiles in **Fig. 4a**, b revealed reversible oxidation process at all investigated electrodes, and the reduction to oxidation currents ratio (I_{pa}/I_{pk}) is about 1.00. From **Fig. 4a** it is evident

that the addition of graphite carbon nitride and MOF-derived nanoceria particles separately in CPE enhanced electrochemical response, while the best electrochemical response in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ test solution was recorded at CPE modified with their combination. The highest peak current was reached with the optimal amount of 10% of this binary composite in CPE and from (Fig. 4b) is evident that further addition of the modifier would only significantly decrease the peak current. The same conclusion was revealed from the EIS study recorded in the same test solution. The semicircle at the EIS spectra and following up linear part of the curve can offer information about charge transfer resistance and diffusion process on the electrode surface. In this regard, it can be seen from Fig. 4c and d that the semi-circle region of the modified CPEs was reduced compared to unmodified CPE, which implies that the cerium oxide and graphite carbon nitride, particularly in their optimal amount of 10% in binary composite, significantly improves the charge transfer reactions which occur at the interface.

Figure 4. a) CV profiles of CPE doped with CeO₂ and g-C₃N₄ (pristine and in composite) recorded in 0.1M KCl solution containing 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ redox couple (scan rate: 50 mV/s); b) CVs of MOF/CeO₂/g-C₃N₄ modified CPEs with different amounts of modifier; c,d) EIS spectra of the investigated electrodes in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ solution.

3.3 Electrochemical behavior of guanine at MOF/CeO₂/g-C₃N₄ modified electrode

CPE-modified electrode with chosen MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄ binary composite in optimal content was used in further experiments to study the electrochemical behavior of guanine by cyclic voltammetry studies in Britton-Robinson buffer compared with the electrochemical response at pristine CPE and in pH range from 2.0 to 9.0 (**Fig. 5**). One sharp irreversible anodic peak from guanine oxidation at 0.96 V can be seen in **Fig. 5a** on both electrodes (modified and pristine CPE) in pH 3.0 at a scan rate of 50 mV/s. Electrooxidation of GU at MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE is highly promoted by electrode modification and the peak current recorded at the modified electrode is 3.5-fold higher compared to pristine CPE. As can be seen from **Fig. 5b**, the peak current has been changed and moved towards more positive potentials by increasing pH from 2.0 to 9.0. The relationship between peak potential (E_{pa}) and pH was linear (**Fig. 5c**) and it can be described by the following equation (1):

$$E_{pa} \text{ (V)} = 1.12 - 0.051\text{pH}; (R = 0.9869) \quad (1)$$

The slope of 0.051 V/pH strongly implies that an equal number of protons and electrons are included in the electrode reaction process. pH 3.0 was chosen for the optimal pH value of BR buffer, due to its sharp and well-defined peak shape, the highest current (**Fig. 5c**). This pH was used in further CV experiments and the development of the analytical procedure.

Figure 5. a) CV profiles with and without 100 μM of GU at MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE and the same concentration of GU at pristine CPE in BR buffer pH 3.0; b) Effect of pH at MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE. The scan rate of 100 mV/s; c) The effect of pH of BR buffer on peak current and peak potential.

3.4 Effect of scan rate and the diffusional response

CV profiles on different scan rates and relationships derived from this study can provide important information and kinetic parameters about the electrochemical process at the electrode surface. The effect of scan rate (in this study: 10, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150 mV/s) was presented in **Fig. 6a**. The linear relationships between peak current vs square root (**Fig. 6a**,

inset graph above) and the logarithm of peak current vs logarithm of scan rate (**Fig. 6a**, inset graph below) imply that reaction on the MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE is controlled by diffusion on a rate-determining step while the adsorption and/or other specific interactions on the electrode surface are negligible. The following equations were derived from the obtained results by linear regression fitting (Equations 2 and 3):

$$I \text{ (A)} = -9.86 \times 10^{-7} + 5.97 \times 10^{-7} \times v^{1/2} \text{ (mV/s)}^{1/2}; \text{ (R} = 0.990) \quad (2)$$

$$\log I \text{ (A)} = -6.61 + 0.62 \times \log v \text{ (V/s)}; \text{ (R} = 0.998) \quad (3)$$

As can be seen, $\log I$ vs $\log v$ resulted in a straight line with a slope of 0.62 and this value is close to the theoretical value of 0.5 which once again suggested the diffusion-controlled process [46].

Tafel plot derived from the rising part of CV recorded at a scan rate of 25 mV/s (**Fig. 6b** and inset plot) corresponded to the linear regression equation (4):

$$E \text{ (V)} = 0.071 \log I \text{ (A)} + 0.1347; \text{ (R} = 0.997) \quad (4)$$

The Tafel plot slope of 71 mV is close to the theoretical value of 60 mV, indicating that two electrons were involved in charge transfer in the electrooxidation process of GU at MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE. The small slope of the Tafel plot suggested a fast electron transfer with minimal kinetic barriers. Diffusion-controlled process at electrode interface ensures sustained reaction rate, better quantitative detection, fouling resistance and stable and reversible sensor response. Diffusion-controlled sensors where the analyte is consistently available at the electrode surface and continuously replenishes itself from the bulk solution making it that concentration gradients drive the reaction are ideal for detecting analytes like guanine in biological samples [47,48]. From Tafel slope electron transfer coefficient α can also be obtained. This slope equals to $2.3RT/Fn(1-\alpha)$, where R and F are the Gas and Faraday constant, T is absolute temperature, n is the number of electrons involved (in this case two) and α was calculated to be 0.58. The standard heterogeneous rate constant of the reaction, k^0 , was calculated from Laviron's equation (5) for the irreversible electrode process. k^0 has a value of $2.86 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, suggesting fast electron transfer between GU and MOF₄CeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE surface. (The formal potential, E^0 , is 0.9381 V and was obtained from the intercept of E_p vs v by extrapolation to the vertical axis to $v = 0 \text{ mV/s}$.)

$$E_p = E^0 + \left(\frac{2.303RT}{\alpha nF} \right) \log \left(\frac{RTk^0}{\alpha nF} \right) + \left(\frac{2.303RT}{\alpha nF} \right) \log v \quad (5)$$

Figure 6. a) Effect of scan rate (10, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150 mV/s) on CV profiles of 100 μM of GU at MOF_dCeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE in BR buffer pH 3.0; (inset graph above-plot of peak current vs square root of scan rate; inset graph below-plot of log peak current vs log scan rate). b) CV of GU at a scan rate of 25 mV/s and chosen data for construction of Tafel plot (inset graph-Tafel plot derived from graph b); c) Suggested mechanism of electrooxidation of guanine.

Equations (1) and (4) in summary suggested electrooxidation of GU at MOF_dCeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE, in correlation with previously ascribed in literature [49–51]. The first oxidation $-2e^-$, $-2H^+$ occurred during the reported complex mechanism, including two-electron transfer processes: E₁, followed by a chemical step, and E₂ to form 8-oxoguanine (peak visible in this study) (**Fig. 6c**), and then 8-oxoguanine can further undergo reversible $-2e^-$, $-2H^+$ oxidation and rapidly hydrolyze [52].

Bearing in mind previously reported conclusions [52], probably the high influence of the chemical step upon the E₂, as a rate-determining step during the all used scan rates from 10 to 150 mV/s existed at MOF_dCeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE. This diffusional response of GU at the electrode is not highly driven in nature, and it is difficult to achieve on carbon electrodes and modified electrodes. Almost all of the reported GU sensors showed a typical surface adsorption-controlled process [15,17–23,52], even those that have CeO₂ in their constitution [20,21]. This adsorption-prone behavior was investigated by tailoring different carbon electrode materials and explained due to the high domination of adsorbed species during the electrooxidation of GU at carbon materials [52]. This adsorption could be blocked by special pretreatment of the

surface during the preparation of the electrode (by cleaning with acetone for example) [52], or using some electrode modifiers more resistant to absorption, as was the case with MOF_dCeO₂/g-C₃N₄, used as electrode modifier in this study. The binary composition of electrode modifier with dominant CeO₂ over carbonaceous material g-C₃N₄ could be crucial for the achievement of diffusional response in the CPE matrix, bearing in mind that unmodified CPE also showed diffusional response [53]. The diffusion-controlled process was also achieved before, by modification of GCE with gold-platinum nanoclusters/reduced graphene oxide [24] and Cu–CeO₂ coated multiwall carbon nanotube composite [25].

3.5 Development of the analytical procedure

From an analytical point of view, the diffusion-controlled process of electrochemical reaction at the surface of the electrode is more desirable than surface absorption due to faster response times, improved sensitivity, reduced interference, wider dynamic range, and better overall reproducibility of sensor measurements. After the characterization of the electrode process and obtaining kinetic parameters, an analytical procedure and method are developed.

Primarily, an analytical technique was chosen comparing the electrochemical responses of two of the most used pulse techniques, square-wave and differential pulse voltammetry without optimization and under operating conditions suggested by the equipment manufacturer. As can be seen from this the **Fig. 7a**, the peak potential for SWV is twice higher than that recorded by the DPV technique. The advantage is also that SWV is much faster than DPV. This method is usually used for the determination of analytes in which the charge transfer is very fast, the better results obtained with this method additionally confirm the fast transfer of electrons over the electrode surface, highlight the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrochemical reaction and the excellent performance of the selected material. Due to higher and more pronounced peak currents, the square-wave voltammetry was chosen. From our research experience, SWV was proved to be a better technique compared to DPV for quantification of analytes (dopamine and lipoic acid), although they have irreversible peaks [31,42], while caffeic acid which possess reversible peaks was better determined with DPV than SWV [33]. The parameters of the technique were systematically varied and optimal ones were established: the pulse amplitude was 50 mV, the frequency was 70 Hz, and the potential step was 5 mV. Under optimal conditions, SWV profiles of different concentrations of GU (0, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7, 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 μ M) at MOF_dCeO₂/g-C₃N₄/CPE were recorded in BR buffer pH 3.0 (**Fig. 7b**) and corresponded calibration curve which expressed concentration dependence of

peak current was presented at **Fig. 7c**. The linear relationship for the working range of 0.5 to 100 μM of GU was described by equation 6:

$$I (\mu\text{A}) = 4.410 + 0.105 \times C_{\text{GU}} (\mu\text{M}); (R = 0.997) \quad (6)$$

Figure 7. a) A comparison of GU responses differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and square wave voltammetry (SWV). b) SWVs for different micromolar concentrations of GU at $\text{MOFdCeO}_2/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{CPE}$ in BR buffer pH 3.0. c) Corresponded calibration curve.

The detection limit of 0.12 μM was calculated from the equation $LOD = 3s/m$, where s is the standard deviation of the blank solution and, m is the slope of the calibration curve. As can be seen from Table 1, the proposed GU sensor has some of the widest working ranges, along with $\text{NpNiMn}_2\text{O}_4$ modified graphite paste electrode [15], electrochemically modified CPE [24,26], and activated glassy carbon electrode with ultrafine carbide nanocrystals confined within porous nitrogen-doped carbon dodecahedrons (PNCD) synthesized by adding molybdate to ZIF-8 followed by annealing [17]. $\text{MOFdCeO}_2/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{CPE}$ is comparable and even possesses better LOD than other reported GU sensors, especially comparing reported chemically and electrochemically modified carbon paste electrodes [18,22,23,26] (except for $\text{In-CeO}_2/\text{GCPE}$, which is more suitable for determining lower concentrations of GU [21]). This comparison confirmed the high analytical performance of $\text{MOFdCeO}_2/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ -modified CPE and developed an analytical procedure for determining guanine.

Table 1. Comparison GU electrochemical sensors in analytical parameters

Electrochemical sensor	Linear range (μM)	LOD (μM)	Ref.
$\text{NpNiMn}_2\text{O}_4/\text{GP}$	0.5-100	0.3	[15]
$\text{PPyox}/\text{MWNTs-MoS}_2/\text{GCE}$	5-30	0.17	[19]
$\text{CeO}_2/\text{MWCNTs}/\text{GCE}$	5-50	0.01	[20]
$\text{In-CeO}_2/\text{GCPE}$	0.07-34	0.0119	[21]

FeOMCPE	10-70	5.3	[18]
MgO-MWCNTs-MCPE		0.92	[22]
CuO NPsMCPE	1-80	0.687	[23]
AuPtNCs-modified GCE	1-200	0.06	[24]
Cu-CeO ₂ /MWCNT/GCE	0.2-6	0.128	[25]
GU-MIP-AuSPE	0.05-0.5	0.00125	[16]
AuNPs/MC-PNCDs/AGCE	0.5-160	0.0721	[17]
Electrochemically modified CPE	3.31-331.1	0.331	[26]
	(0.5-50 μg/ml of GU)*	(50 ng/ml of GU)*	
MOF ₂ CeO ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄ /CPE	0.5-100	0.12	<i>This work</i>

*Original data in the article

3.6 Stability study, interferences and real sample analysis

The stability of the prepared modified electrode was studied to investigate reproducibility and long-term applicability. **Fig. 8a** shows the relative error of five consecutive SWV measurements of 7 μM of GU, taking the initial one as a comparison for the others. The relative standard deviation for those five times repeated measurements of GU at the selected pH and optimal experimental conditions was found to be 1.6%, and the electrode retained 94% of the peak current response for initial peak current after 15 days of storing in the ambient conditions after use.

A selectivity study for guanine determination was done in the presence of various inorganic ions and biological compounds. The developed sensor exhibited satisfactory anti-interference ability as the addition of 100 μM of fructose, glucose, lactose, sucrose, citric acid, folic acid, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Al³⁺, NH₄⁺, F⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, and NO₃⁻ led to a relative error of less than ±5.0% in guanine response. The effect of possible interfering ingredients that could be ordinarily found in urine sample was also examined (**Fig. 8b**). Dopamine (DOP) and ascorbic acid (AA) were added in 5:1 ratio to 10 μM of guanine, while uric acid (UA) was added in ratio 0.05:1, because proposed sensor showed high sensitivity toward UA. From the graph, it can be seen that for the addition of AA no peak occurred, the addition of UA significantly reduces dopamine-derived signal, but the GU response remains almost unchanged. Finally, 5 mL of urine was added to 20 mL of the studied solvent with all compounds on it, and the same influence over DOP was observed. The change of peak current for GU determination was less than 5%, in all cases, showing the high tolerance towards the studied potential interfering

biomolecules and indicating the successful real sample determination in the presence of all these compounds.

Figure 8. a) The change in current densities for five consecutive SWV measurements; b) SWV profiles with and without the presence of interfering compounds in the determination of guanine under optimized experimental conditions.

Bearing in mind previously obtained results of good analytical performances, stability, reproducibility, and selectivity, the $\text{MOFdCeO}_2/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{CPE}$ was finally confirmed by sensor applicability in real sample analysis. Before testing, the collected urine samples were acidified for preservation and stored in the refrigerator at 4 °C. 1 mL of urine was added in 20 mL of BR buffer solution pH 3.0 and this solution was spiked with different amounts of guanine for testing of the prepared electrode and developed electrochemical method. The concentrations of the GU were determined from the calibration curve used for determining GU concentration in spiked urine sample (Fig. 7c), and these results and recovery values are listed in Table 2. The proposed method possesses satisfactory accuracy with no/or negligible matrix effect, particularly due to the high oxidation potential of GU at this electrode. Hence, the proposed sensor and developed analytical method were validated in the accurate determining of guanine and further is ready to be used in real sample analysis. Although our proposed sensor was successfully applied for the determination of guanine in model urine samples, it is possible that the determination of this compound would be faced with significant challenges in complex samples like blood and saliva. The problem can be a complex sample composition in which proteins and lipids can be absorbed on the surface of the electrode and interfere the signal. Sample viscosity could also affect sensor performances Bearing all that in mind, it is possible

that analysis of complex biological samples like blood and saliva can request sample pretreatment or standard addition procedure and recording calibration curve for GU in matrix.

Table 2. Recovery data for guanine determination was observed for spiked human urine samples.

Sample No	Detected* (μM)	Added * (μM)	Found* (μM)	Recovery (%)
1.	0.00	7.00	6.87±0.04	98.1
	6.87±0.04	3.00	10.32±0.36	103.2
	10.32±0.36	3.00	13.45±0.28	103.5
2.	0.00	20.00	19.66±0.45	98.3
	19.66±0.45	4.00	24.22±0.18	100.9
	24.22±0.18	4.00	28.48±0.42	101.7

^a An average of three replicate measurements ± SD

CONCLUSION

Obtained results in this research confirmed that cost-effective, easily prepared, BTC-derived nanoceria/graphitic carbon nitride, could be used as an efficient electrochemical sensor modifier for fast, sensitive, and selective guanine determination in test solutions and model urine samples. This binary composite with dominant nanoceria possesses a cubic structure, with an average crystallite size of 7 nm and as a modifier, embedded in carbon paste matrix, provides a fast and stable diffusional response which contributes to analytical performances (wide working range and low detection limit) of developed electrochemical guanine sensor. Our further work will focus on lowering the limit of detection, achieving a diffusional-controlled reaction on a slightly structurally improved combination of MOF-derived nanoceria and carbonaceous materials and exploring the possibility of application of this and mentioned sensors in complex biological samples like blood and saliva with minimal sample preparation required. Based on this one and similar works, the great potential of producing metal oxide nanoparticles and metal/carbon structures from MOF precursors could be observed. Fabrication of MOF-derived materials in combination with conductive carbon materials and networks could be a successful pathway for designing various functional materials with favorable sensor performances toward bioactive compounds.

CRedit author statement

Branka B. Petković: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Hristo Kolev:** Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Djordje Veljović:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Software, Validation. **Dalibor M. Stanković:** Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Bratislav Antić:** Project administration, Resources, Supervision. **Miloš Ognjanović:** Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing.

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